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EDITORIAL

It is with immense pleasure that I present the MZU Journal of Literature and Cultural Studies, Volume XII, December 2025. The contributions in this issue reflect the complex and evolving nature of both literary and cultural discourse. The research papers, while diverse in subject matter, share a commitment to asking fundamental questions that may redefine one's understanding of the fabric of society.

From oral traditions to digital storytelling, interdisciplinary approaches including cultural studies, postmodernism, gender studies, and post-apocalyptic concepts, have been integrated. Through textual and ethnographic research, folktales, poetry, novels, and film are examined by situating them within contemporary society. Beyond examining the notion of metanarratives to present relevant arguments, the thirteen papers in this volume are selected with the hope of broadening new directions and fostering critical dialogue that is essential for future inquiry within the field.

To ensure the quality and maintain standard of the journal, all research papers undergo an originality check and a double-blind peer review process by experts in related areas. It is hoped that the varied and valuable insights into the dynamics of literary studies, culture and identity of Northeast India and beyond will enrich existing scholarship in these areas.

Prof. K.C.Lalthlamuani
Editor

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**The Detective as Author:
Narrative and Deduction in Edgar Allan Poe's Auguste
Dupin Stories**

Dr. Debjani Dutta
Independent Researcher, Munich

Abstract

This paper will analyse the modes of the detective fiction genre by choosing to examine the three C. Auguste Dupin stories penned by Edgar Allan Poe. As one of the progenitors of detection in fiction as we know it today, Poe introduced myriad constructs, chief amongst them the key role of ratiocination. Through the lens of the author function as adumbrated by Michel Foucault, this paper will explore the extent to which Dupin's encounter with the intricate complexities of deduction may be parsed through the discursive practice of the author as a potential investigator. As Poe depends on many examples of acuity and observational perspicacity in the manner in which he builds his detective's character and actions, it will be fruitful to mount a challenge as interrogator of both the textual fabric and the architectonics of écriture which a discerning reader may comprehend in a binding of the author's function as giving status to a text. The aim will be to sound whether Dupin's inferences which helped lay the foundation of enigma and investigation may actually help synthesize apperceptions of the detective as author and actor in his own case(s).

Keywords: *author, detective, ratiocination, enigma, narrative, deduction, conceit, discourse.*

Introduction: Detective Lore

Detective fiction is a genre that relies on a time-tested formula to augment itself – the commission of a crime and the discovery of the perpetrators responsible for such a crime. The structure of this genre is focused on the search for the criminal – almost an “obsession with discovering ‘who done it’” (Kayman, *From Bow 3*). The mainstay of a detective tale is a problem at the heart of the plot, and the manner in which deduction is deployed to unravel the said problem. As identified by the literary theorist Tzvetan Todorov in his seminal essay ‘The Typology of Detective Fiction,’ there is a double logic to the proponents of such a story, a duality of thematization which anchors the events. There is in the first instance “the story of the crime” and in the second, “the story of the investigation” (Todorov 295). Todorov, referencing the Russian Formalists, focuses on the signifying elements of narratology to help extoll the virtues of detective fiction – he calls on the distinctions between the *fabula* (story proper) and the *syuzhet* (discourse or plot) (Todorov 296) to bear on what I call the interpretive dynamics of detection in a novel or a short tale. The *syuzhet* works on the *fabula* to lay bare a detective tale to the discerning reader – the distinction lies in understanding the crime as corresponding to events similar to reality, and the telling of the tale as “the plot [...] the way the author presents it to us.” (Todorov 296). The events of the crime are described after the fact, and the reader follows the detective first in the reconstruction of the crime and eventually in undoing the metrics of the first story. One can then assume that there are essentially gaps in the narration which the detective, by virtue of the discourse structure, attempts to fill by rewriting “into plenitude, coherence and significance by the detective’s closing

explanation” (Kayman, *From Bow* 13). Many critics argue about these structural architectonics – while they agree that there is a duality or a double structure in the art of deduction, they disagree on certain of the anecdotal interpretations that can be divined. Martin Kayman, in his study of mystery and detection talks of the same two structures defined by Todorov, but asserts that while these two stories might be dual in nature, they end up referring to the same series of events, a model that “contains its own gloss” (18-19) – one that is contingent on finding meaning by recounting the events leading up to/surrounding the crime, while enabling the reader to try and come to terms with two successive narrative levels. Peter Hühn also notes that the detective novel also bargains a lot on the moment when the hidden dynamics are revealed to the public and the police, which will have a particular desired effect on the perception of the detective held by the same public and officials. He refers to this part as “the ‘publication’ of a particular story, namely that of the crime.” (451-452).

Keeping the distinctions thus outlined in mind, one arrives at the fictional production of Edgar Allan Poe. Commonly considered one of the first progenitors of detective fiction, Poe birthed the arrival of Chevalier C. Auguste Dupin, an amateur investigator (at least initially) who relies on the use of reason, acute observation, and inference to find solutions to some very complicated crime scenes. When introducing the analyst for the first time in “The Murders in the Rue Morgue,” Poe describes his methods as one based on the most minute examinations, finding almost the devil in the details. In each of the three Dupin stories, the Prefect G. from the Paris police and his staff always fall short of finding a solution to the crime which besets them at that moment in time. Moreover, the story

and discourse happen on two levels, but the point of departure for this paper to examine the link between the two parts will be the concept of the author function as adumbrated by Michel Foucault in his 1969 lecture “What is an Author?” The attempt will be to see whether Dupin can function as an author of the mysteries he so clearly and clinically solves, and the manner of exactitude with which the narrator-assistant performs the role of the reader (in essence leading Poe’s audience reader) in mapping Dupin’s narratorial conceits and inferences. As Foucault wants to determine “the functional conditions of specific discursive practices” (114), so this paper will test whether there is a framework of nascent details on which Dupin relies to bring order to a society newly destabilized and suffering the effects of a transgression of accepted societal norms.

The Modes of the Author Function

When speaking on the function of the author as he sees it, Michel Foucault argues that we must look beyond the history of just an individual author when deciding the merits of a cultural text. Foucault wants to lay aside the usual considerations that accompany “the sociohistorical analysis of the author” (115), instead choosing to focus on a systematic valorisation of the contextual fundamentals of a given text, one that sheds light on the shared affinities between an author and his text, where the text “points to this figure who is outside and precedes it” (115). The writing of the text might be its own referent and yet not preclude the necessity of an “exterior deployment” (Foucault 116). The manner of the composition is a challenge to the established order, where it (the author’s writing) engages in an act of reversal of the usual conditions of functioning. Further, in a discussion of the total effacement of an author’s

creative stimulus from a text, Foucault weds this to the question of death. He delves into a study of the Greek narrative epic to support his point, where the hero leads a life of feats and sacrifices and is consecrated by a magnificently written death (117). He further threads Scheherazade's endless stories in *The Arabian Nights* to fend off death for just another day as an aspect of what he calls the "inversion of murder [...] to exclude death from the circle of existence." (117). Foucault conjectures that in the present moment of writing, any effort to interrogate the author and his proclaimed/declaimed intentions is via his very absence from the text, in his linking his persona to death and thereby developing what I call a mistake syndrome – becoming heavily bonded to his own intentional fallacy and losing the thread of the plot. Furthermore, Foucault asks two questions of any work – a) that it should never be restricted to a mere appreciation of the architecture of the textual fabric, but rather insist on asking questions of the concept which underlays the composition; and b) the conceptions and conditions of *écriture* which set out to designate the motives of a written text, including the perceived "primordial status" (120) given to writing and the *a priori* implicit assumptions which often give rise to obscure commentary (without the necessary complementarity or context) (122-123). These declarations, when together viewed through the lens used to examine the narrative strictures and structures that determine detective fiction and specifically in the case of Auguste Dupin's use of ratiocination, will throw light on the manner in which he deploys himself as a sleuth in search of the truth. This truth is concealed under layers of hidden meaning, hindered by the obscure investigative methods of the Parisian police, and done no favours by the plodding and direct dissimulation of three

major newspapers in their quest to establish a certain picture of a heinous crime. Discourse is diverted to create a mayhem of ineptitude in each of the three crimes which Dupin solves, and the first clue of the nature of each is left in the imprimatur of their respective titles – murders, mystery, and the need to purloin. The presence of a detective figure, a person who will assume the responsibilities which state officials have failed to carry out, is thereby already indicated, but it is the duality of the detective as author and the coparcenary interests of the reader/narrator as detective, that will be of preponderance in the remaining discussion of each of the stories.

Of a Monster in a Locked Room, or “The Murders in the Rue Morgue”

In this 1841 short story, Poe starts by a lengthy discussion on the merits of analysis and inference. The initial pages introduce us to the unnamed narrator who analyses the mind of the analyst. It is made evident that the analyst is “fond of enigmas” (Poe 487) and the measure of his acumen is to be found more in a game of draughts than in chess or even whist. Armed with acute observational skills and a highly fine-tuned balancing act that adequately keeps emotion in check in order to clinically draw judgements, the analyst is always ingenious even when the ingenious man is not analytical, and is “truly imaginative” (Poe 489) when the merely ingenious are but barely fanciful.

The murders are described as “extraordinary” (Poe 494), at once sensationalising the ensuing events. The descriptions of the events are borne by a newspaper; the same technique Poe will use in his second Dupin tale. The papers report that at about three o’clock on the day in question loud and ferocious

shrieks disrupted the peace of the Quartier St. Roch neighbourhood. These sounds emanated from the house on the corner belonging to Madame and her daughter Camille L'Españaye, an otherwise retiring family. On following the sounds and arriving on the fourth floor of the building, the group of worried onlookers discover a scene of the “wildest disorder” (Poe 494) with furniture upended, a razor smeared with blood, tresses of uprooted human hair and a bag containing a considerable amount of cash – nearly four thousand francs’ worth. The body of the daughter is found stuffed up the chimney chute, with bruises and discolorations of skin. The mother is found on the yard in the rear of the building, her throat cut and head nearly dismembered from the body. What follows in the newspaper report, which is recounted in the tale one after the other, are various testimonies from persons present who describe their acquaintance or lack thereof with the murdered women. Ranging from the *gendarme* who attended on the scene to the L'Españayes’ banker to the corner shop tobacconist (amongst others), all testimonies point to the hearing of at least two voices, one gruff and the other shrill. But they all fail to pinpoint the origin of the language in which this heated conversation took place. There is a plethora of details in the reportage which tumble one over the other, with individual biases coming to the fore – while most agree the gruff voice as possibly French (overhearing words akin to ‘sacré,’ ‘*diable*’ and ‘*mon Dieu*’), they always misrepresent the nationality of the second tone. A clerk is falsely accused of the murder and the case seems forcibly closed when Dupin decides to take a look of his own.

In talking of the importance given to the name of an author while examining the contours of a text, Foucault adumbrates

that the difference lies in the manner of the approach and reception given to such texts as do bear the name of the author (123). The impact of the discourse is seen in the trajectory of its circulation, because once the name of the author is reliably taken along with the critical contentions of the text, it is not possible to “be immediately consumed and forgotten” (123). If we take the charmed introduction to the analyst as the naming of the author, we can trace how Dupin’s deductions derive and carve the rest of the narrative of *Rue Morgue* from here on out. The narrator’s implicit assumption on the reportage is that it is an “insoluble mystery” (Poe 500), contrasting sharply against Dupin’s showcasing the theme of the Paris police’s rank incompetence – “we must not judge of the means by this shell of an examination” (Poe 500). He goes on to state that while the Paris police might very well not be lacking in intellect, they are woefully beggared when it comes to the application of methods suited to a unique crime.

Where the police err is in forming a bigger picture of the circumstances and in assuming immediately that the crime committed must be due to human agents, even when the gory details suggest otherwise. Kayman thinks that this error is not only on behalf of the police, but also the reader (led by the narrator’s nudges) – the general assumption of criminal behaviour deriving from human motives (*From Bow* 138) leading to the effective mismatch. Dupin, I would argue, exists here in a breach – his method of ratiocination reaches beyond the humdrum police processes to a search of the entire neighbourhood and in particular a thorough examination of the rooms inhabited by the mother-daughter duo. Details like a broken window sash and the question of egress from what is effectively a locked room – the key was found latched to the

door from the inside – allow Dupin to make his deductions sound legitimate and above contest. On examining the scene, the bodies of the murdered women and also the tufts of grey hair pulled from their human roots, Dupin is not averse to making assumptions. He correctly presumes that such power as has been wielded by the perpetrator may not be human, and searches for evidences that may support his thesis. Dupin, therefore, scrutinizes and interprets the clues left behind, which separates his methodology from the plodding police effort. Dupin assumes a “preternatural character of agility” (Poe 508) on the part of the murderer (to perform ingress and egress by the window as had been done) and the fact that the murderer ignores the gold. He ties the “brutal ferocity of these deeds” (Poe 510) to a *facsimile* of the indentations and discoloration on the throat of the daughter, and zeroes in on Georges Cuvier’s description of an Orang-outan as the butcher behind the crime. By the use of empiricism, Dupin identifies a non-human source of the neighbourhood massacre, and by increased reflection on the origin of one of the voices and a piece of ribbon tied in a knot peculiar to a Maltese sailor, he concludes correctly that a French sailor on a Maltese vessel lost control his brute pet which led to the chain of circumstances. The impossibility of domesticating a brute beast and the Orang-outan’s instinct of doubling its master (by copying his motions of using a razor) develop into a parable of an imprisoned monster who wreaks havoc in a locked room. In this mode, a detective is born, makes a handful of logical deductions, refutes the unimaginative conclusions of process-bound police, and helps establish a category of narrative where the authorial powers of the investigator act as a contract to the circulation of the fictional detection.

Inauthenticity and Aberration in “The Mystery of Marie Rogêt”

In writing the tale of Marie Rogêt, Poe made a departure from his previous tale of ratiocination. While in the first he stresses on the intellectual prowess of his investigator as the distinguishing factor in the solving of the crime, in the second Dupin tale Poe attempted to write about the real-life mystery story of the disappearance and murder of the American Mary Rogers (Kopley 44). The case of Mary Rogers was written about with much fanfare in the New York papers of 1842, and scholarly critique has taken note of the prompts which Poe took from the newspapers to fashion each of Dupin’s arguments in Marie Rogêt’s case. Richard Kopley, in his exhaustive study of the source material of the Dupin stories (*Edgar Allan Poe and the Dupin Mysteries*), ties the theories of the secret amour and naval officer angle to information gleaned by Poe in papers mentioned in the notes to the 1845 version of the tale (46-63) – namely the New York *Evening Post*, the *Evening Tattler*, and the weekly round of the *Brother Jonathan*. Stephen Knight in his review of Poe’s contribution to the genre of detective fiction, pronounces this tale as rather a clumsy attempt on the part of the writer to saddle his detective with a case that was yet reaching its own resolution in real time (Knight 27-29). The shrewd feats of mind-reading and a balanced empiricist approach which was on display in the tale preceding, is here replaced by mere debunking of newspaper postulates.

A chief point of difference in the Marie Rogêt case is the acceptance of a payment by Dupin in order to take on the task of the unsolved mystery. It is mentioned in the story that the Prefect G made an offer of an unnamed sum to Dupin, who

accepted it and upon fulfilling the terms of his contract is paid the sum due (Poe 594). This marks a shift in approach of the Chevalier from being merely an amateur to a considered professional – he charges for his services, and this is followed up with much emphasis in the third and the last tale. In the aftermath of the Rue Morgue case, Dupin's renown had spread through certain quarters – arguably the first instance of reputation-building of the detective which will help them join hands with the police to solve crimes in the annals of literature. But it is the debunking of the reported narratives which assumes importance in trying to pinpoint the manner of the inferences Dupin draws. Dupin debunks each of the articles and contends that mere theorizing without reference to facts cannot unravel a complicated problem. Poe concludes that the law or the law courts mostly guide themselves on the principle of the evidence, without paying any particular and needed heed to the singularities of cases which do not fit the regular mould. This praxis, while admirable for trying to get to the truth the greatest number of times (Poe 611), fails miserably when it comes to the adjudication of individual errors, both in character and method. Dupin asseverates that the Marie Rogêt murder was the work of an individual and he proves his *a priori* speculation by going back to the biography of Marie as covered by these very same newspapers. By searching through her historical propensity to run away from home for a stretch of time, Dupin steadily dispels the untruths circling her murder. He fastens on the theory of the singular murderer who tried to dispose of her body clinically, does away with the idea of a gang being inculpated in the criminal activity of her death, and identifies the *modus operandi* of a possible naval officer who had an on-off affair with the victim. Hence, communications that were

actually red-herrings were sent to the news dailies, to deter the authorities from the pursuit of the real culprit.

The calculus of Dupin's influence cannot really save this tale from the weakness of its constructions. The inauthenticity which permeates this tale is reflected in the critical consideration it has garnered over the years. Depending as it does on too much exposition and too many borrowings of real events, the discourse is characterised by aberrations from the truth. The question of the author-function in this text is difficult to answer – Poe the author is working from a series of scripts, building a fiction which in the end did not match the reality of events in New York (a death-bed confession and the abortion theory, see Kopley 47-52). The newspaper editorials, acting as *quasi* monitors of truth, are themselves rife with incomplete data and inept conclusions. Their individual reputations are “no guarantee of their authenticity” (Foucault 125). Foucault postulates that value may only be attributed to a text when its information can be verified by the perceived “sovereignty of the author” (126). In this tale, one might reasonably say that neither the editors, nor the actual author or the fictional detective-as-author has any power over the location of meaning in the text. The reliability of the evidences is very much in question, as are the techniques employed (armchair analysis by Dupin and the editors) All of their respective conclusions are merely disproved conjectures, a signal of the failure of the author-function to guide a narrative to its own evidential closures.

Conceit and Concealment in “The Purloined Letter”

The third and last of the stories to feature Auguste Dupin, “The Purloined Letter” is more in the line of an enigma than any of the ones that went before. Unlike in the previous tales,

here the identity of the perpetrator is well known and an accepted fact. In fact, I would argue that knowledge of the Minister D by Dupin acts as the most crucial artefact in this tale of ratiocination and wit. Dupin's ability of logical analysis and firm examination of evidence is something the discerning reader will now be much familiar with. Concomitantly, the inability of the Paris police to handle a complex case by themselves is also an established narratorial point. The case rests thus – a letter belonging to the Queen (referred to throughout the text as a most royal personage and her gender pronoun) has been whisked away – purloined from right in front of her eyes – from her private boudoir, by a person with considerable standing in court, the Minister D. All of this was done in the presence of the King who was completely ignorant of both the presence of such a sensitive letter and its pinching by the Minister in front of their very eyes. The Queen's letter alludes to certain sensitive information which it is in her interests to conceal from the King. The Minister D is a crafty man who can quickly read the situation in a room – he immediately recognizes the handwriting of the upended letter on the Queen's desk and realises its value to the Queen, and the unique position the letter would bestow on the hands of its possessor. He proceeds to purloin the letter from right in front of the Queen's eyes by a sleight of hand, and thereby asserts the right to exercise his powers of extortion over the Queen. The word 'purloin' derives from the Anglo-French verb alluding to a prolonging or a postponement – verily setting something aside for a time. The situation of the last Dupin story is the same – the Minister D plays a game of cat and mouse with the Queen, always exercising the threat of using the letter against her, but knowing that his powers will be delimited if he ever actually

uses it – “it is this possession, and not any employment of the letter, which bestows the power. With the employment the power departs” (Poe 829). Also, the Minister is very much aware that the Queen knows his intentions and will be willing to try and reclaim possession of the document at any expense – what Dupin calls “the robber’s knowledge of the loser’s knowledge of the robber.” (Poe 828). None of the Prefect’s approaches, meticulous and ingenious as they are, yield the desired result. In her study of the gothicism(s) present in the architecture of detective fiction, Miranda Michelle states that the Paris police are now at the danger of having committed the same mistake thrice over – they have not learnt from past experiences of mishandling key cases (6-8). As Dupin declares, the Prefect is too attached to his own methods to ever engender a change. He thinks all fools are poets and because the Minister D has a slight reputation at poetry, the Prefect considers him an open and shut case of fool. But it is the wedding of the prowess of a mathematician alongside the imaginative *nous* of a poet that stand the crafty Minister in good stead – essentially keeping him out of the reach of the law.

In his “Seminar on the Purloined Letter,” Jacques Lacan focuses on the significance of the letter. He advances his theory of the three glances by positing what each of them get to see, correlative to the Queen, the Minister and Dupin. (Lacan, “Seminar on the Purloined Letter”). Not only does Lacan raise the question of the all-knowing glance, he also questions the bipartite structure of the text – the story of the investigation and the story of the crime. He declares that Dupin’s “would-be disciple” endows a new subtext to the tale by his act of delegation (Lacan, “Seminar on the Purloined Letter”) – by recording the story, by being the link of classical detective fiction

who ties the story of the plot and the setting (Hühn 452). Moreover, by playing on the theme of concealment throughout the tale, Poe reveals the mastery of detective fictionalization over the reader. The contents of the letter are forever hidden from the reader; it can only be subjected to mere suppositions. The critic Peter Thoms rightly states that this tale in particular is a vehicle for the display of narrative technique and control in the weft of crime and detective fiction (Thoms 141). The possession of sight, unhindered by bias - as is the case with Dupin, allows him to outwit the Minister D in what is essentially a matching of intellects. On a search of the Minister's premises, Dupin alights on an old scratched letter lodged in a cardboard rack and calculates precisely that it is the letter in demand. This is because Dupin reads the Minister's mannerisms too well for his opponent to hide anything - not for once does he consider the Minister anything less than methodical and imaginative. Dupin resorts to the creation of a *facsimile* again (after using the same tactic in "Rue Morgue") and swaps the document for a fake of his own creation. In speaking of the author-function, Foucault speaks of the "plurality of egos" - one who is instrumental in the "circumstances of the composition" and the other who "concludes a demonstration within the body of the text." (130) He then goes on to point out the existence of a possible third ego - "one who speaks of the goals of his investigation, the obstacles encountered, its results" (130). We might extrapolate these specific declarations to the triad of the present tale - the Minister as the originating subject of discourse, who seemingly purloins a letter and starts weaving great power, the narrator who acts as a vehicle for the dissemination of the details of the investigation and the function of Dupin as a detective-author, who tethers the tale to its logical conclusion.

By relying on symmetry and synthesis, Dupin transforms from an amateur to a full-fledged professional (in the story he is written a handsome cheque by the Prefect for reclaiming the letter). Moreover, he serves the final double deceit on the criminal – not only by creating a copy of the purloined letter, but also by folding it and marking it with the exact same scratches of deception used by the Minister, and enjoining a codified message referencing the Atreus-Thyestes revenge arc.

Conclusion

In the assessment of most critics, “The Murders in The Rue Morgue” and “The Purloined Letter” stand as pillars of “the fountainhead of modern crime fiction” (Rzepka 74). A locked room is wedded to a crime left unsolved, essentially begging the question – “whodunnit? An apparently simple case is presented with the rare task of asking how to outwit a master criminal – without in the process harming the interests of the Queen. The second tale remains a mystery, as its title (Marie Rogêt) suggests – more so because it was a fictional attempt on Poe’s part and also because “the case was solved before Poe published the end of his story, and the solution he proposed was wrong.” (Rzepka 75). In the detailing evident in the Dupin stories, Poe helped constitute both narrative and plot as key markers of detection, one incomplete without the assistance of the other. Peter Thoms asserts that Dupin often uses a shock tactic to unsettle his readers – “manufacturing the very anxiety he is supposed to soothe” (143) – as seen in the manner of his confrontation with both the sailor in the “Rue Morgue” and the casual theatrics of small talk in the chambers of the Minister D. Keeping all the tactics employed by Dupin and originated by Poe in mind, we should nevertheless remember the

importance of the bipartite structure – for without the *syuzhet* working on the *fabula*, the reader might well have been left asunder in the game of reason and observation. Poe assumes the role of the reader but does not presume an admeasurement of similar intellect between his detective and reading audience. Therefore, the role of the narrator/assistant is paramount in helping readers to follow the reason behind the deductions. The genius of the detective is often clear only in retrospect, and never without the modality of the sidekick (Rzepka 77).

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